

InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

D2.3 Co-design and co-creation plan for stakeholders

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Summary

This preliminary co-design and co-creation plan for stakeholders collects the main co-design and co-creation activities planned for InBestSoil project that need from stakeholder collaboration to deliver on their results. These activities have been planned considering the needs and involvement of stakeholders defined in D2.2 – Stakeholder mapping for LHs and LLs. The plan includes clear objectives and implementation details for an effective engagement of all stakeholders involved in the different activities of the project. The plan has been developed in consultation with all consortium partners, involving principally WP leaders in consultation with LH and LL coordinators. This plan will be updated as needed during the project lifetime and these changes alongside the description of all activities carried out will be included in a final updated deliverable (D2.4) In M48.

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Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Authors		
ZABA	Izaskun de Allende [ZABA]		
	Alba de Agustín [ZABA]		
	Maite Alonso [ZABA]		
	Collaborators		
	FGN, ACTYVA, UPCT, UVigo-CVAN, UniZG, MRU-LAB, SILAVA, EKO, CMCC-AGRIS, FiBL.		
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1. Introduction

The InBestSoil co-design and co-creation plan is a collaborative initiative of InBestSoil partners to support project results development and delivery in a participatory way. From the definition of suitable indicators for soil health ecosystem services, to developing new sustainable business models or incentive schemes, InBestSoil is committed to define collective solutions for protecting and enhancing soil health together with its 7 Lighthouses (LH) and 2 Living Labs (LL), and their local stakeholders. These LHs and LLs have been created following the ENoLL criteria but have not been funded through the specific Living Lab calls of the Soil Mission; therefore they cannot be considered as Soil Mission LightHouses and Living labs.

This document includes the steps followed during the co-creation plan development and validation process, and all the activities, defined in collaboration with InBestSoil partners, that will be implemented throughout the project lifetime. The deliverable reflects on the potential limitations that could arise during the implementation phase and recommends strategies to overcome these, serving as a guideline for the implementation and follow up of all the planned activities. The co-design and co-creation plan will be updated by the end of the project (M48) to include the description of all the implemented activities, its outcomes, and learnings (D2.4).

Besides constituting a planning tool for InBestSoil co-creation activities, the plan also aims to inspire other EU projects to effectively plan and manage their own project collaborative initiatives.

Disclaimer on Living Lab (LL) and Lighthouse (LH) terminology

In the context of the InBestSoil project, the terms “Living Lab” (LL) and “Lighthouse” (LH) are used in accordance with the definitions and nomenclature established in the Grant Agreement and Description of Action. These terms refer to project-specific case studies and multi-actor co-creation settings that support research, innovation, and stakeholder engagement activities.

However, it is important to clarify that these LLs and LHs are not formally established or certified under the Horizon Europe Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe”, nor do they correspond to officially recognised Mission Soil Living Labs or Lighthouses. Instead, they represent project-level co-creation environments and demonstration sites that align with Living Lab principles to varying degrees.

The activities implemented within InBestSoil aim to strengthen these sites in terms of governance, stakeholder engagement, and co-creation capacities, thereby advancing their maturity and their ability to operate as impactful multi-actor co-creation experimental sites.

This deliverable also refers to Task 2.4 (“From local to regional/national: building LLs based on existing LHs”) as defined in the Grant Agreement. In line with the original Description of Action, this task aims to expand and structure stakeholder engagement around selected sites. However, it is important to note that InBestSoil will not establish or certify new Living Labs in the formal sense of the Mission Soil framework. Instead, the activities implemented under this task focus on strengthening their co-creation and stakeholder engagement capacities to amplify their impact as soil health ecosystems.

Contribution to InBestSoil’s objective

The objective of InBestSoil is to co-create a framework for investment in conservation and recovery of soil health, by developing an economic valuation system of the ecosystem

services delivered by a healthy soil, and its incorporation into business models and incentives. This will allow public and private organizations to give economic value to their actions over soil health, co-design strategies with local stakeholders, and work collectively to deliver national and EU policy ambitions. InBestSoil will provide data, evidence, tools and models to assess how investment in soil health can contribute to the transition to a long-term resilient and sustainable use of soil, using **7 lighthouses and 2 living labs, which provides a total of 9 study areas across 4 biogeographic regions** from Europe (Boreal, Continental, Atlantic, Mediterranean), and different land uses (agriculture, forest, urban, mining), as models for cocreation and co-design (multi-actor approach, responsible research and innovation and open science). InBestSoil is a 48-month project that started in January 2023, and it includes 19 partners from 10 European countries. The project is divided into 7 WPs.

This deliverable is planned within *WP2 Stakeholder communities for co-creation, co-innovation, and co-learning*, and it contributes to InBestSoil's objective by ensuring that different valuable perspectives from a diversity of land uses and bioclimatic regions will be incorporated to the development of project results. The co-creation plan is also closely related to Deliverable *D2.2 InBestSoil stakeholder mapping for LHs and LLs*. In fact, the stakeholders' identification and mapping is to be used when designing and implementing each of the proposed co-creation activities.

Structure of the deliverable

This document constitutes a planning tool to co-design and co-create solutions in collaboration with InBestSoil stakeholders for soil quality, defining the objectives, timings, and procedures for these interactions. The main sections of this document are structured as follows:

Chapter 2 introduces the co-creation processes and their role in the Mission Soil and presents an overview of InBestSoil's approach to the co-creation plan.

Chapter 3 presents step-by-step guide to use the InBestSoil co-creation plan and its validation process.

Chapter 4 describes the co-creation activities that complete the co-creation plan. Each activity is described in an individual activity sheet.

Chapter 5 includes the potential limitations found during the development and first activities' implementation process and recommendations to overcome and successfully implement the plan.

2. Co-creation processes for soil health

Chapter 2 introduces co-creation processes as the basis of the co-design and co-creation plan, providing background on what co-creation is, for whom it is intended, and why it is of relevance for InBestSoil and Mission Soil projects in general. The concept of co-creation processes in multiple soil health projects is showcased, and an overview of the co-design and co-creation plan for the InBestSoil project is presented as part of the Mission Soil initiative.

Co-creation definition and relevance

What is co-creation?

Co-creation processes refer to the involvement of stakeholders at different project stages to collaboratively define common issues, develop solutions, products, or ideas. The EU Missions propose a novel approach to R&I and its articulation with policies and mechanisms to promote the uptake of results from research on the ground: A comprehensive, co-created and cross-sectoral R&I agenda is proposed to help overcome the current landscape of fragmented research in the EU while mobilising public and private actors to work together towards a common goal.ⁱ Specifically, the second operational objective of the *Mission Soil: A Soil Deal for Europe* is to Co-create and upscale place-based innovations to improve soil health in all placesⁱⁱ.

Who participates in co-creation processes?

A diversity of agents can participate in co-creation activities, from policy makers to civil society organizations, industry, or academia. The Mission implementation is based on the recognition that people and their actions need to change to make a rapid shift happen. Hence, the focus is on societal change (e.g., amongst land managers, spatial planners, civil society, consumers, researchers, advisors, regional stakeholders and policymakers, industries) and citizen engagement.

Why co-creation?

Co-creation processes facilitate experience-based learning, leverage on resources diversity, new sources of value creation, new ideas generation and testing, learning from stakeholders, partnerships, and networks creation. Under the Mission Soil, co-creation is considered a building block of "Living labs and lighthouses"ⁱⁱⁱ, addressing the need to close the science-practice gap and co-develop and upscale innovations that are adapted to the diversity of soil, geographic and socio-economic conditions. Living labs are collaborative initiatives to co-create knowledge and innovations while lighthouses are places for demonstration of solutions and exemplary achievements.

Considering the complexity of soil health and its role in climate change and biodiversity conservation, multidisciplinary strategies are required to face present and future challenges. According to the Mission Soil Implementation Plan, actors in the living labs will develop an understanding of the soil health and related ecosystem challenges in their area, of their knowledge and technology needs, build on existing or knowledge created under the R&I programme, and come up with new research questions.

Co-creation approach in InBestSoil

How does InBestSoil approach co-creation?

Co-creation within InBestSoil has been structured through WP2 *Stakeholder communities for co-creation, co-innovation, and co-learning*, which will cover the entire project duration and its main objective is to create and strengthen stakeholder communities along the project LHs and LLs, as a central hub for the performance of all other WPs. WP2 is divided in four tasks to achieve the following three specific objectives:

- **Engage and involve** a wide variety of local, regional, national, and European stakeholders including companies, public authorities, investors, and civil society.
- **Establish short- and long-term collaboration** schemes and platforms for the effective co-creation, co-innovation and co-learning process and sustainability of the project by dynamizing LH communities and building LLs around them.
- **Implement participation, co-design, and co-creation methodologies** to fully integrate key stakeholders' knowledge, perceptions, and interests in all project activities and beyond.

To achieve these, co-creation in InBestSoil focuses on designing and implementing appropriate engagement activities organised together with project partners to collectively co-design and co-create project results. The main co-creation activities of the project contribute to the different WPs and the results will be reflected in the corresponding deliverables, focusing on (figure 1):

1. Co-defining **soil health indicators** for each Ecosystem Service, responding to land users, managers and/or policymakers' priorities and needs (WP3).
2. To assess the benefits and barriers for **carbon farming** and which measures would benefit land users (WP4).
3. Understanding which **business models and incentives** best support land users would and/or managers that decide to implement sustainable practices (WP5 - WP6).
4. Understanding and finding solutions to **barriers and needs** already identified by land users, managers, or policymakers in terms of implementing sustainable practices (WP4-WP5).
5. To understand the role of small-scale **innovations led by farmers (or land users)**, to adapt existing technologies to agri-ecological practices (WP4 – WP5).
6. To propose new **policy measures** that can support farmers and land users or managers transition to best soil health practices (WP6).

Figure 1: Co-creation initiatives and relationships in different project Work Packages (WPs).

Who is involved in InBestSoil co-creation activities?

The co-creation plan requires from various stakeholders' profiles both to be designed and to be implemented.

During the design phase of the co-creation activities, both scientific and local partners have worked together to define the co-creation activities that best suit project needs. WP leaders have identified the co-creation needs to deliver the project objectives included in their respective project tasks, and LH and LL coordinators have the role to contextualise and fine tune these activities according to local needs and opportunities. All these proposed co-creation activities are gathered and aligned in the co-creation plan (chapter 4), aiming to facilitate its successful implementation by identifying synergies and proposing engaging strategies.

For the implementation phase, a wide variety of stakeholders will be needed to carry out the planned activities. LH and LL coordinators will be responsible for reaching out to diverse stakeholder profiles with the support of WP leaders to implement the plan.

Who is this plan for?

The plan is meant to be used by InBestSoil consortium partners for the effective implementation of the co-creation activities defined for the project ensuring meaningful communication between WP and task leaders, project LH and LL coordinators, and local stakeholders. However, the document also aims to serve as inspiration and example for other EU projects that would like to design and implement a co-creation plan in their projects.

What can we find in the InBestSoil co-creation plan (chapter 4)?

This plan collects all the co-creation activities planned for the lifespan of the project. The plan serves as a guide to WP partners and LH and LL coordinators to overview project activities that require from stakeholder participation.

Having a plan in place, allows strengthening synergies between WPs and coordinating these activities for a successful implementation. It facilitates the communication between WP partners and LH and LL coordinators, providing clarity on the role and responsibilities of each project partner in the co-creation activities. Questions such as "how is the stakeholders' knowledge and perspectives included in the project?", "what is expected from project partners or stakeholders?" or "when is their participation needed?" are addressed by this plan.

The description of each activity is summarised in an activity sheet as part of section 4 and a summary of these activities is presented in table 1:

Co-creation activity*	Lead	Timeline	Status
WP2 Stakeholder communities for co-creation, co-innovation, and co-learning			
Selection of three InBestSoil frontrunner sites for capacity building as co-creation experimental sites	ZABA	Dec 2024	Not started
Capacity building for two LHs to evolve into LLs.	ZABA	Apr/Jun 2025	Not started
Co-definition of the digital platform features.	LGI	Apr/Jun 2023	Completed
Collaborative definition of usability options for the digital platform.	LGI	Jun 2024	Completed

WP3 Economic valuation of the soil ecosystem services and the impacts of soil interventions			
Co-definition of suitable indicators and standardized metrics for the LCA and evaluation of ecosystem services and disservices provided by soil in different land uses.	UVigo/ UPTC	Mar/July 2023	Completed
Measurement of cultural ecosystem services for soil health.	UPTC	Sep/Nov 2024	Not started
WP4 Impacts and scalability of current soil health interventions across Europe			
Collaborative mapping of current business models archetypes, drivers, and barriers for SMBs related to soil health in the EU.	WU	May 2024	Completed
Ex-post evaluation of soil health business models I.	FiBL	Sep 2023 Sep 2024	Ongoing
Ex-post evaluation of soil health business models II.	FiBL	Jun 2025	Not started
Impact assessment of forestry business models.	LGI	Jun 2024 July 2025	Ongoing
WP5 New business models for soil health			
Validation of protocol for co-design of new business models.	UOE	Mar 2024	Completed
Training on how to use the integrated research methodology and common protocol for co-design of new business models.	UOE/ WU	Sep/Nov 2024	Not started
Executing the protocol for co-creating a sustainable business model portfolio.	UOE & WU	Mar/Sep 2025	Not started
Reflection on portfolio for their business model co-design after completing various co-creation activities.	WU/ UOE	Mar 2027 (TBC)	Not started
WP6 Policy and incentives to facilitate investment in soil health			
Pre-selection of policy and economic incentives for soil health.	CMCC	Mar 2024	Completed
Conducting a SWOT analysis with LH/LL communities using financial models.	CMCC	May 2024	Completed
Using policy framework analysis to explore a successful implementation of the incentive schemes for ecosystem services delivered by healthy soils across multiple scenarios.	CMCC	From Dec 2024	Completed
Sharing of the soil health certification in carbon farming framework with LH/LL stakeholders.	CMCC	June 2024	Completed
Develop policy recommendations based on WP2-WP5 outputs.	CMCC	Dec 2026 Dec 2027	Not started
WP7 Communication, dissemination, and exploitation			
Co-create a survey to gather relevant information from stakeholders to identify a topic suitable for the media and public.	JUNE	Jun/Oct 2024	Ongoing
Collaborative messages co-creation for communication & dissemination.	JUNE	Apr 2024	Completed

Table 1: Summary of InBestSoil co-creation activities.

* Additional activities might be planned if the project requires of stakeholders' input in an activity not identified by the time this deliverable is published.

3.Co-creation plan structure and validation

Chapter 3 introduces the structure of the co-creation plan and its validation process. First, the template of the activity sheet used to describe each co-creation activity is presented. Next, the validation of the co-creation plan and of the activity sheets by consortium partners (WP partners and LH and LL coordinators) is detailed.

Note: The completed activity sheets detailing the activities are presented in Chapter 4, Co-creation plan.

Co-creation activity sheets

The activity sheet is divided into 4 sections, providing a comprehensive definition of the activity:

Section 1: Activity coordinators

This section indicates the project partners involved in the coordination of the activity: task leader, partners collaborating, and partner responsible for coordinating the activity.

Section 2: What?

This section explains what the activity is about: the objective and the description of the co-creation activity.

Section 3: When? And how?

This section presents the time frame during which the activity is to be conducted and the format in which the activity will be conducted. Indicating the date, confirmed, or estimated, allows for coordinating and aligning with participants' agendas. Selecting the activity format, tools, and language to be used in advance is also key for preparing the activity.

Section 4: For whom is this activity? And why?

This section describes the target group of each activity. This can include participants from different profiles, e.g., farmers, policy makers, public bodies, and, or LH and LL coordinators. Identifying how many participants of each profile are needed and how to reach out to them (e.g., available networks or contacts) is key for preparing the activity.

In addition, for a successful stakeholder engagement, the benefits of participating need to be stated, considering that each stakeholder profile might benefit in a different way from participating in the activity (e.g., increasing knowledge, being part of networks, providing input for policies etc.)

In addition, this section describes how the outcomes of the activity relate to the project. For example, the outputs of the activity can feed an upcoming activity or contribute to strengthening the knowledge created within the project.

Table 2 presents the activity sheet template with the corresponding explanation on the expected information in each category:

Activity title	<i>Clear title.</i>
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	<i>e.g., Under which partner falls this activity within the GA?</i>
Co-organisers	<i>Which project partners are involved in organization of the activity?</i>
Facilitator	<i>Who is expected to conduct the activity?</i>
What?	
Objective	<i>Clear objective.</i>
Description of the co-creation activity	<i>Use bullet points. Be specific. Complete description.</i>
When and how?	
Time frame	<i>Expected or confirmed time frame.</i>
Format	<i>Some examples of potential answers are: Workshop, survey, interview, focus groups? Specify online or face to face.</i>
Tools	<i>Some examples of potential answer are: Miro, google forms, Microsoft teams?</i>
Language	<i>English / Local language.</i>
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	<i>Which project partners or stakeholders are actively participating in the co-creation activity?</i>
What is in it for participants?	<i>What can the participants expect as a take home learning?</i>
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	<i>What are the expected outcomes for the WP/ project? How do the outcomes of this activity add to the project?</i>

Table 2: Co-creation activity sheet template.

Validation process

The validation of the co-creation activities facilitates alignment in terms of goals, approaches, and timings, strengthening the synergies between different WPs and tasks and avoiding overlaps. In addition, it ensures that the co-creation activities are well described and that there is a mutual understanding between WP partners and LH and LLs coordinators.

The co-creation plan was validated in three steps:

Step 1: Validation workshop

The validation workshop (figure 2) was conducted during the consortium meeting in Latvia, on 7th June 2024. The workshop consisted of three parts: description of the co-creation plan, the showcase of an activity sheet as an example, and a group discussion on the co-creation plan.

As an example, the co-creation activity "Training CS coordinators of LLs and LHs on how to carry out the protocol for co-creating a sustainable business model portfolio" from WP5 was selected. For the group exercise, the 22 participants, including WP and task leaders

and LH and LLs coordinators were divided into smaller groups to discuss the opportunities and limitations of the co-creation plan. To facilitate the discussion, the participants were asked to collaboratively answer four questions regarding the presented co-creation activity:

- Is this activity clear enough? If not, what is not clear?
- Is there any information missing? Is there something else you would like to know?
- Do you see any limitations/ challenges in the development of this activity?
- In which way can this activity be useful for you, for stakeholders and for others?

Figure 2: Co-creation validation workshop during the consortium meeting in Latvia.

The outcomes of the workshop have been grouped into the following themes: request for clarification, identified limitations and general remarks:

Request for clarification:

- Participants identified the need for a more explicit objective description, for more details on the activity, on the workshop structure and timing.
- Participants recommended simplifying the activity sheets: text to be more straightforward.
- Regarding stakeholder engagement, participants identified as an important point to clarify the profile of stakeholders needed for each activity, the information to be requested from/given to stakeholders, and to better describe the benefits of participation for stakeholders.
- In general, the need to better contextualize the activity within the InBestSoil project was observed.

Identified limitations for the development of the activities:

- Language barriers and online activities were identified as challenges for the success of the activities, recommending workshops in person using local language. In addition, cultural aspects should be considered in the communication.
- Other challenges are the need to reach different audiences, understanding the role of each participant, and getting stakeholders involved in several workshops.

General remarks for when conducting co-creation activities:

- The benefits of participating in activities needs to be clear for stakeholders. Each stakeholder might benefit in a different form or might be attracted by different reasons, for example, input for policies (governments), expertise (municipalities), or ideas to grow the business (farmers).
- The use of scientific jargon should be avoided when communicating with stakeholders. A best practice from another project was shared in which two protocols are used, a more scientific one and another one with the jargon translated for stakeholders.
- The feedback was integrated in the co-creation plan: the layout of the activity sheet was adapted making it more user-friendly summarising ideas and clarifying the information collected in each section. Step 2: Validation of the co-creation plan by WP partners

Step 2: Validation of the co-creation plan by WP partners

Based on the results of the validation workshop (step 1), the co-creation plan was updated by WP2 leaders and shared with all WP partners who need to organise co-creation activities as part of their research.

The WP partners reviewed the updated co-creation plan and provided feedback on limitations (e.g., challenges to coordinate the activity) and opportunities (e.g., synergies between activities). The input received by the WP partners was incorporated into the co-creation plan.

Step 3: Validation of the co-creation plan by LH and LL coordinators

For the validation of the co-creation plan by LH and LL coordinators, bilateral meetings between each task leader and the LH and LL coordinators are being organised prior to each co-creation activity. During these meetings, the task leader presents the activity to the LH and LL coordinators for them to provide feedback on limitations (e.g., challenges to engage certain stakeholders and/or timing) and opportunities (e.g., potential benefits for stakeholders). This input, key for ensuring a successful implementation of the activity, is incorporated by task leaders to adapt the co-creation activity.

By the time this deliverable was submitted, all completed activities have been validated by LH and LL coordinators and the rest will be validated in the coming months.

To ease the validation process for each activity, bimonthly meetings have been scheduled for WP and task leaders to have the opportunity to present their co-creation activities to LH and LL coordinators, creating a space for discussion and feedback before these activities are implemented. Three bimonthly meetings have been conducted already and there are upcoming bimonthly meetings scheduled until the end of the project. In addition, bilateral meetings will be organised between WP and task leaders and LH and LL coordinators as needed.

4. InBestSoil co-creation plan

Chapter 4 presents the co-creation plan, which consists of the compilation of all the co-creation activities planned in InBestSoil. These are presented within their activity sheet, and grouped in six sections based on the WP they belong to. Each section introduces the corresponding activities and the links between them. The activities, the inputs and the (expected) outcomes of the co-creation activities per WP are summarized in diagrams.

Stakeholder communities for co-creation, co-innovation, and co-learning

The creation of stakeholder communities to enable co-creation processes within the project requires effective ways for collaboration such as a collaborative digital platform that could facilitate the interactions between different stakeholders. In addition, and as the Mission Soil initiative evolves, there is increasing emphasis on the development of place-based, multi-actor co-creation environments for soil health across Europe, aligned with recognised Living Lab principles.

To support these processes, the co-creation activities included in this section (Figure 3) aim to:

- strengthen selected InBestSoil frontrunner sites by enhancing their governance structures, stakeholder engagement and co-creation capacities, aligning them with ENoLL principles.
- develop and maintain a digital collaboration platform to support interaction and knowledge exchange among the InBestSoil sites and Living Labs (Table 5, Table 6).

Figure 3: Diagram representing the co-creation activities in WP2, inputs (in brown) and outputs (in green).

Co-identification of three InBestSoil LH/LLs for capacity building as co-creation experimental sites

Activity title	Co-identification of three InBestSoil frontrunner sites for capacity building as co-creation experimental sites
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 2.4. From local to regional/national: building LLs based on existing LHs (WP2, task leader: ZABA).
Co-organisers	LGI
Facilitator	ZABA
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To identify to what extent InBestSoil LH and LLs comply with ENoLL's descriptions, characteristics and existing guidelines. – Identify limitations and opportunities for InBestSoil LL/LHs to strengthen their structures and frameworks as multi-actor co-creation experimental sites. – Co-identify three frontrunner sites to evolve into co-creation experimental sites. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<p>An online workshop during which:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The concept of multi-actor co-creation and related governance, engagement and operational aspects are presented to LH/LLs coordinators. – A first exercise is conducted by each LH/LL coordinator to assess the current status of their case study in terms of stakeholder engagement, co-creation practices, and organisational configuration, as well as to identify potential areas of improvement. – A second exercise to be conducted by each LH/LL coordinator: SWOT analysis of their case study focusing on its capacity to function as an effective co-creation experimental site. After the workshop, bilateral meetings are organised between ZABA and each LH/LL coordinator to further discuss their case and identify additional capacity-building actions. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	January 2025 – April 2025.
Format	Workshop & bilateral meetings.
Tools	Miro board & Teams platform.
Language	English; Spanish.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
All LH coordinators.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Participants will gain an understanding of key elements of multi-actor co-creation approaches, including stakeholder engagement and collaborative innovation processes. – Each LH/LL will be guided through the process of assessing their current capacities (including the identification of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats) related to their future role as co-creation experimental sites and in alignment with ENoLL guidelines. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ project	

- Identify the potential drivers and barriers affecting the capacity of frontrunner sites to operate as impactful co-creation experimental sites.
- Build operational frameworks to strengthen the selected sites' governance structures, stakeholder engagement and co-creation capacities.

Table 3: Co-identification of three InBestSoil LH/LLs for capacity building as co-creation experimental sites

Capacity building for three selected LH/LLs to become co-creation experimental sites

Activity title	Capacity building for three selected LH/LLs to become co-creation experimental sites
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 2.4. From local to regional/national: building LLs based on existing LHs (WP2, task leader: ZABA).
Co-organisers	LGI
Facilitator	ZABA
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The aim is to improve three selected LH/LL's alignment with ENoLL Living Lab criteria 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<p>Session(s) during which three InBestSoil frontrunner LH/LLs are guided through the process of co-defining an operational framework to strengthen their capacity as co-creation experimental sites in alignment with ENoLL criteria.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mapping of stakeholders and identification of potential organisations to collaborate with. – Discussion on available business models and potential funding sources in collaboration with WP5. – Integration of key InBestSoil components supporting the development indicators and sampling frameworks, business models and incentives schemes. – Targeted training to strengthen their community of stakeholders. – Development of an operational frameworks for each the three frontrunner sites to become impactful co-creation experimentation sites. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	September 2025 – September 2026.
Format	Training session. The number of sessions is to be determined depending on the needs.
Tools	Online or face to face tools for collaborative work: Miro (online) etc.
Language	English; Spanish; Other local language (with local partners' translation support).
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
<p>WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6. InBestSoil frontrunner LH/LLs who have shown interest and maturity levels to become co-creation experimental sites aligned with ENoLL criteria.</p>	

What is in it for participants?
-The selected InBestSoil LH/LLs will strengthen their governance and stakeholder ecosystem to operate impactful co-creation environments for soil health innovation.
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project
- Strengthened stakeholder communities around three InBestSoil LH/LLs to support co-creation, co-innovation, and co-learning in soil health innovation ecosystems.

Table 4: Capacity building for three LH/LLs to become co-creation experimental sites.

Co-definition of the digital platform features

Activity title	Co-definition of the digital platform features.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 2.3 Development and maintenance of InBestSoil a digital collaboration platform for LHs and LLs (WP2, Task leader: LGI).
Co-organisers	A design committee has been set up with partners from all WPs.
Facilitator	LGI
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The aim of this series of workshops is to define all the features to be deployed for the InBestSoil platform as well as other general questions important to define before starting with the development of the platform. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<p>This issues about the InBestSoil platform are defined via Mural online tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Tags for categorising users, groups, and resources. – The user typology and registration system. – The main functions and management of access rights. – The overall design of the platform. – Rules for using the platform. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	5 workshops from April to June 2023.
Format	Workshop.
Tools	Mural visual online work platform.
Language	English.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
All WPs partners.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Be able to include important tags for the WPs in the platform. – Contribute with WPs input in the selection of relevant words, bigrams, and trigrams. – Think about the different users and their access/permissions. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Get all necessary information for LGI developers to start their work on the platform. 	

Table 5: Co- definition of the InBestSoil digital platform.

Collaborative definition of usability options for the digital platform

Activity title	Collaborative definition of usability options for the digital platform.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task leader	Task 2.3 Development and maintenance of InBestSoil a digital collaboration platform for LHs and LLs (WP2. Task leader: LGI).
Co-organisers	Partners from all WP. All consortium was invited.
Facilitator	LGI
What?	
Objective	
<p>This activity aims to incorporate the opinions of consortium partners and LH/LL coordinators to enhance the InBestSoil platform and achieve the following individual goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Better define the platform's scope. – Collect ideas on the possible uses of the platform. – Improve the services provided for users. – Brainstorm possible new features. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Before the workshop: Consortium partners and LH/LL coordinators receive an email outlining the main goals of the activity. – During the workshop: Using a MURAL board, participants are guided to answer various questions related to the workshop goals. – After the workshop: LGI come up with proposals to enhance platform usability and engagement. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	25 th June 2024.
Format	Workshop.
Tools	Teams and Mural.
Language	English.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
All LH/LL coordinators and partners from all WP.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Their opinion is valued to improve the use of the platform. – Learn from different opinions and options to use the platform. – Contribute with their input to new possible features of the platform. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<p>Using the feedback of this co-creation activity the platform would be improved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Adding new features. – Creating some recommendations. 	

Table 6: Digital platform usability workshops.

Economic valuation of the soil ecosystem services and the impacts of soil interventions

The economic valuation of soil ecosystem services and soil intervention impacts, requires from LH and LL coordinators' engagement and local stakeholders' participation to define the most suitable indicators framework to measure ecosystem services provided by healthy soils, and more specifically, to define indicators for cultural ecosystem services.

These objectives will be reached through two participatory processes (Figure 4) involving LH and LL coordinators and their local stakeholders. Firstly, from an initial set of soil health ecosystem services indicators the most appropriate indicators to measure quantitative and qualitative ecosystem services provided by a healthy soil will be selected (table 7). Secondly, the measurement of cultural ecosystem services, with the previously selected indicators, will be carried out (table 8).

Figure 4: Diagram representing the co-creation activities in WP3, inputs (in brown) and outputs (in green).

Co-definition of suitable indicators to evaluate ecosystem services and disservices provided by soil in different land uses

Activity title	Co-definition of suitable indicators to evaluate ecosystem services and disservices provided by soil in different land uses.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 3.1. Co-definition of suitable indicators and standardized metrics for the LCA and evaluation of ecosystem services and disservices (WP3, Lead: UPTC).
Co-organisers	ZABA
Facilitator	UPTC: elaborate survey and analyse responses. LH/LL coordinators: distribute survey. ZABA: Follow up and collect responses.
What?	
Objective	
Co-define suitable indicators for the evaluation of ecosystem services in Soil Health.	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – A survey with a set of indicators related to soil health ecosystem services and translated to all InBestSoil local languages is distributed to LH/LL coordinators. – LH/LL coordinators support distributing the survey among local stakeholders. – LH/LL coordinators and stakeholders fill in the survey on indicators to evaluate ecosystem services and disservices provided by soil. – Follow up emails on the completion of the survey are sent by ZABA every week. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	March-July 2023.
Format	Complete an online Survey.
Tools	Outlook forms.
Language	Local language.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
The survey is to be completed ideally by 10 stakeholders per profile and LH/LL: Landowners and farmers; Researchers; Public managers; Civil society organizations.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Learn about ecosystem services related to soil health. – Contribute with their knowledge on the selection of indicators to measure soil health. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Generate a co-defined list of indicators for measuring key parameters to determine ecosystem services provided by healthy soil. – The set of indicators and the process followed will be used for soil sampling within InBestSoil T3.2. It will also be presented to EUSO and other EU organisations to obtain approval and validity also at EU level. – The selected cultural ecosystem service, will be measured in the co-creation activity "Measurement of cultural ecosystem service in soil health". 	

Table 7: Co-definition of suitable indicators.

Measurement of cultural ecosystem services for soil health

Activity title	Measurement of cultural ecosystem service in soil health.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 3.2. Measurement of soil health indicators to quantify the delivery of ecosystem services provided by soils (WP3, leader: UPCT).
Co-organisers	ZABA, all LH/LL coordinators.
Facilitator	LH/LL coordinators: distribute the survey.
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To measure cultural ecosystem services in each LH/LL in collaboration with LH/LL coordinators and local stakeholders. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Collaborative development of the survey: LH/LL coordinators are asked to provide two pictures of their LH/LL landscapes before and after InBestSoil interventions. These photos are integrated in a survey used to measure the cultural ecosystem services. – Distribute the survey: UPCT shares the survey with LH/LL coordinators. LH/LL coordinators are asked to distribute the survey with local stakeholders. – Complete the survey: LH/LL coordinators and stakeholders are asked to complete the survey. – Follow up and reminders on survey completion in collaboration with LH/LL coordinators. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	LH/LL coordinators send the photos by 15th September 2024. Launch Survey: October 15th (InBestSoil bimonthly meeting). Complete the survey by November 2024.
Format	Online survey.
Tools	Online survey tools.
Language	English and LH/LL local languages.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
<p>LH/LL local stakeholders to respond the survey: ideally 20 stakeholders per each LH/LL. Ideally 5 stakeholders per category: Landowner and farmers; Researchers; Public managers; Civil society organizations.</p> <p>LH/LL coordinators respond to the survey and provide two pictures of their case studies.</p>	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The participants' perspectives will be included in the measurement of cultural ecosystem services. – Participants will have the opportunity to express to what extent healthy soils and landscapes contribute to wellbeing and healthy lifestyles. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Measurement of the cultural ecosystem service provided by soil health in InBestSoil LH/LLs (included in deliverable 3.2 Report on economic valuation of ecosystem services and disservices in LHs). 	

Table 8: Measuring cultural ecosystem services for soil health.

Impacts and scalability of current soil health interventions across Europe

Analysing existing innovation processes on soil health and expected benefits when upscaling the improved soil health practices will also entitle consultations and co-creation approaches during the project lifetime, to ensure that the literature review on existing business models and their potential drivers and barriers meets real contexts', and to evaluate the eco-efficiency and impact of existing business models and interventions in soil health, in particular in relation to forestry business models.

To achieve these objectives, four co-creation activities are planned within this section (Figure 4). Firstly, a collaborative mapping of drivers and barriers for soil health business model in EU will be conducted with relevant stakeholders to complete the information gathered through literature review (table 9). Secondly, if existing carbon farming practices increase farm eco-efficiency alongside other impacts will be analysed together with local stakeholders (table 10, table 11). Finally, interviews to gather data on key indicators for analysing the impact of forestry practices on business models will be conducted (table 12).

Figure 5: Diagram representing the co-creation activities in WP4, inputs (in brown) and outputs (in green).

Collaborative mapping of drivers and barriers for SMBs related to soil health in the EU

Activity title	Collaborative mapping of drivers and barriers for SMBs related to soil health in the EU.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 4.1. Sustainable business models: state of the art of current archetypes, drivers, and barriers (WP4, leader: WU).
Co-organisers	EKO, FiBL and LGI.
Facilitator	WU
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Collect feedback from relevant stakeholders on sustainable business models drivers and barriers and compare it to literature review findings. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Interviews with farmers in the Netherlands about drivers and barriers on sustainable business models. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	May 2024.
Format	Interviews.
Tools	Face to face.
Language	Dutch.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
Farmers from LH7.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Learn about sustainable business models and tools to assess them. – Express their concerns and perspectives in relation to barriers and opportunities in relation to existing business models. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – This activity would help to complement the mapping of sustainable business models (D 4.1). – It would be part of a master thesis project. 	

Table 9: Mapping of drivers and barriers for sustainable business models.

Ex-post evaluation of soil health business models I

Activity title	Ex-post evaluation of soil health business models I.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 4.2. Ex-post evaluation of business models for improving soil health in agriculture (WP4, leader: FiBL).
Co-organisers	LGI
Facilitator	All LL/ LH coordinators.
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To gather information from farmers on whether existing soil health practices increase farm eco-efficiency alongside other impacts. – To present a benchmarking app created for disseminating the results to farmers (the app is used to communicate results and provide further knowledge exchange). – To discuss the survey results with farmers and validate that the results align with field cases and collect feedback to improve the model. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Conduct online surveys with farmers for consultation and feedback gathering on soil health practices and its impacts. – Organise a farmer field day to discuss and disseminate survey data. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	Survey (completed April 2024). Field work: before September 2025 (exact date to be determined).
Format	Online Survey. Farmer field days.
Tools	Survey tool: Limesurvey, R. A benchmarking app is used to analyse the data and for survey results dissemination with farmers. Participatory learning.
Language	English, German, French.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
Survey: Farmers from LHg: 2.800 farmers & Advisory services (Extension centre from LL2 - Ebenrain).	
Farmer Field day: farmers, researchers, and farm advisors (further details to be defined).	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increased understanding among farmers of the soil health performance of their farm compared to similar farms. – Improved awareness among farmers of good practices for soil health promotion. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Knowledge creation: illustrated by scientific publication. 	

Table 10: Ex-post evaluation of soil health business models I.

Ex-post evaluation of soil health business models II

Activity title	Ex-post evaluation of soil health business models II.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 4.2. Ex-post evaluation of business models for improving soil health in agriculture (WP4, leader: FiBL).
Co-organisers	LGI
Facilitator	All LH/LL coordinators.
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To co-validate research findings from previous activities (mapping of business models and desk research) with WP partners and LH/LL coordinators and ensure that these relate to real contexts. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Consultation with project partners on survey results and how these contribute to the creation of soil health business models. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	September 2025.
Format	Online results presentation with project partners. Validation in an online session.
Tools	E-meetings (Digital platform).
Language	English.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
WP partners and LH/LL coordinators.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increased understanding among WP partners and LH/LL coordinators about existing carbon farming business models and the barriers and drivers for its implementation. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Dissemination and validation of results (Deliverable D4.2: Ex-post carbon farming impact evaluation report). 	

Table 11: Ex-post evaluation of soil health business models II.

Impact assessment of forestry business models

Activity title	Impact assessment of forestry business models.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 4.3. Ex-post evaluation of forestry business models (WP4, leader: LGI).
Co-organisers	SILAVA, ACTY, FGN, FiBL.
Facilitator	LGI to conduct interviews and analysis. LH1 (Fundación Global Nature & Actyva) and LH6 coordinators (SILAVA team) to identify foresters and organize meetings.
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To collect data on key indicators to analyse the impact of forestry practices on their business models in Latvia and Spain, with a particular focus on soil health practices (SHP). 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – This activity involves collecting data on key indicators to evaluate the impact of different forestry business models and understand the specific soil health practices (SHP) implemented by forests in Latvia and Spain. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	From June 2024 until July 2025. June 2024: interviews with Latvian foresters (LH6). October 2024: interviews with Spanish foresters (LH1). Until July 2025: back and forth to validate data and analysis with coordinators (LH1 and LH6).
Format	Face to face qualitative interviews.
Tools	Interviews and Interview guide.
Language	English and local language if necessary.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
Local stakeholders including forest owners, managers, and investors from LH1 or LH6. A total of 5-10 participants per LH are expected to take part in this activity.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Participants will gain insights into the impact of various forestry practices, particularly SHP, and contribute to a broader understanding of effective forestry business models. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The methodology and results are intended to be easily replicable and disseminated for other forestry projects. – An ex-post forestry impact evaluation report (Deliverable 4.2) will be produced based on the findings. 	

Table 12: Impact assessment of forestry business models.

New business models for soil health

InBestSoil will co-design together with other value chain actors (e.g., businesses, citizens, local authorities) new business models and strategies for enhancing soil health practices under different land uses. To achieve this, a protocol for co-designing new business models has been created and documented in *D5.1 – Research integrated protocols on how to co-design new business models*.

The co-creation activities described in this section aim at validating the protocol and developing capacity to use the protocol with local stakeholders and to test it with real use cases in some of the InBestSoil LHs to develop their own sustainable business models (Figure 5).

Firstly, the protocol is validated (table 13), followed by a training on the protocol for site coordinators (table 14). Next, the protocol is executed by the coordinators of the selected (frontrunner) sites with the participation of stakeholders and the support of UOE and WU (table 15), in order to develop sustainable business models within three selected sites, strengthening their capacity to operate as Living Lab-type co-creation environments. Finally, the coordinators of these frontrunner sites collaboratively reflect on the implemented sustainable business models (table 16).

Figure 6: Diagram representing the co-creation activities in WP5, inputs (in brown) and outputs (in green).

Validation of protocol for co-design of new business models

Activity title	Validation of protocol for co-designing new business models.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 5.1. Development of a common integrated research methodology and a common protocol for co-design of new business models (WP5, leader: UOE).
Co-organisers	ZABA
Facilitator	UOE
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To present and discuss the sustainable business model's development protocol with LH/LL coordinators. – To validate the protocol with LH/LL coordinators. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<p>The co-creation activity is divided in 5 sections:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Presentation introducing "What and why" of sustainable business models. – An online survey completion. – Discussion on "understanding current case studies", using a collaborative online board. – Introduction to the protocol content. – Discussion on the protocol, a collaborative online board. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	26 th of March 2024.
Format	Workshop and a survey to be completed during the workshop.
Tools	TEAMS and MIRO (Google forms for the survey).
Language	English.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
All LH/LL coordinators.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The participants can contribute with their input in the creation of a protocol that is to be applied in a later stage in their LH/LL. Their input would allow contextualising the protocol, which is expected to result in a more successful implementation and thus, more suitable business models for their LH/LLs. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The validated protocol is available for implementation. – A report of integrated protocols on how to co-design new business models (D5.1). 	

Table 13: Validation of protocol for co-design of new business models.

Training on a common protocol for co-design of new business models

Activity title	Training on a common protocol for co-design of new business models.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 5.3. Design of new business models for soil health: the Triple Layer Business Model Canvas (WP 5, task leader: UOE and WU).
Co-organisers	ZABA
Facilitator	UOE & WU
What?	
Objective	
– To train LH/LL coordinators on the protocol, for them to be able to support the execution of the protocol (including stakeholders' engagement) in a later stage.	
Description of the co-creation activity	
– Participate in a training on the created business model protocol.	
When and how?	
Time frame	From September to November 2024.
Format	Face to face.
Tools	To be defined.
Language	English.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
All coordinators of project LLs and coordinators of LHs who are going to establish an LL.	
What is in it for participants?	
– Each LH/LL coordinator will feel prepared to carry out the protocol steps in their own local context and will have worked with WP5 to craft a timeline of activity dates that align with the needs and status of their case study.	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
– Better prepared LH/LL coordinators which is expected to result in a more successful implementation of the protocol.	

Table 14: Training on a common protocol for co-design of new business models.

Executing the protocol for co-creating a sustainable business model portfolio

Activity title	Implementing the protocol in LH/LLs.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 5.3. Design of new business models for soil health: the Triple Layer Business Model Canvas (WP 5, leaders: UOE/WU).
Co-organisers	All LH/LL coordinators and ZABA.
Facilitator	LH/LL coordinators.
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Development of suitable business models for a selection of LH and LLs using the protocol created by the InBestSoil project. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<p>The activity is divided into three sub-activities, each of them described below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Co-create sustainable business models: The first session is organised to define the scope and the interest of stakeholders in creating specific business models for their case. – Make sense of the problem: Through systematic thinking. – Strategize a business model: develop a business model together with stakeholders. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	Spring-Summer 2025 (exact date to be confirmed).
Format	Three workshop series.
Tools	To be defined by LH/LL coordinators (online or face to face workshop).
Language	Local language.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
A selection of LH and LLs and stakeholders (3 to 7 per LH or LL), the most important and influential ones considering the stakeholder map (D2.2).	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Knowledge on sustainable practices keeping the business profitable. – Peer Networking. – Opportunity to participate in future projects. – New sustainable business model proposed for each LH participating. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The development and implementation of diverse, innovative, and adaptable sustainable business models. – Leveraging collective expertise and fostering collaborative innovation to address sustainability challenges. – Establishing sustainability metrics for continuous improvement, documenting, and disseminating best practices, and generating local economic and social benefits. 	

Table 15: Executing the protocol for co-creating a sustainable business model portfolio.

Reflection on portfolio for their business model co-design after completing various co-creation activities

Activity title	Reflection on portfolio for their business model co-design after completing various co-creation activities.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 5.3. Design of new business models for soil health: the Triple Layer Business Model Canvas (WP 5, leaders WU/UOE).
Co-organisers	ZABA
Facilitator	WU
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To reflect and discuss about the use in practise of sustainable business model portfolio within the project. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
Reflection on the learnings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – LH/LLs present their work. – Discussion and peer evaluation. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	Around March 2027 (to be confirmed).
Format	Face to face.
Tools	To be defined.
Language	English.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
A selection of LH and LLs.	
What is in it for participants?	
An assessment and potential improvement strategies for their business models.	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
An assessment and a summary of improvements for the business models.	

Table 16: Reflection on portfolio for their business model co-design after completing various co-creation activities.

Policy and incentives to facilitate investment in soil health

InBestSoil project aims to analyse policy requirements, barriers and enablers, and economic incentive schemes delivering on sustainable soil management and preserving or restoring soil health in collaboration with project partners and local stakeholders. The forthcoming EU carbon farming certification system will be analysed under the soil health perspective, assessing the opportunity to include additional indicators or general criteria that can feed other instruments like labelling schemes or within policy updates.

To achieve meaningful and local adapted results, a series of co-creation activities have been planned under this section (Figure 6). Firstly, a collaborative selection of policy and economic incentives for soil health will be carried out (table 17). Secondly, a SWOT analysis of the previously selected policy and economic incentives will be facilitated with LH and LL communities (table 18) and challenges and barriers experienced while applying financial schemes to local situations will be analysed (table 19). Finally, the soil health certification in carbon farming framework will be shared and discussed with LH and LL stakeholders (table 20) and policy recommendations will be collaboratively proposed (table 21).

Figure 7: Diagram representing the co-creation activities in WP6, inputs (in brown) and outputs (in green).

Pre-selection of policy and economic incentives for soil health

Activity title	Pre-selection of economic and financial incentives for soil health.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 6.1. Stocktaking; mapping review of policy and economic incentives for soil health (WP6, leader: CMCC).
Co-organisers	ZABA
Facilitator	CMCC
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To present and discuss economic and financial incentives for soil health. – To provide feedback on financial and economic schemes to elaborate a final list. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Before the workshop: LH/LL coordinators receive a document with 79 incentives to read. – In the workshop: Using a collaborative online board, the financial and economic schemes are divided according to soil risks. The LH/LL coordinators are expected to select the financial schemes most appropriate for each of the soil types present in their LH/LL. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	25 th March 2024.
Format	Workshop.
Tools	Teams and MIRO board.
Language	English.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
All LH/LL coordinators.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Knowledge on the potential financial schemes for their LH/LL. – Learn from different financing opportunities currently being used in other LH/LLs. – Contribute with their input in the selection of most appropriate incentives. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – From a preliminary list of 79 schemes, the financial and economic schemes most appropriate for each LH/LL based on their soil risks are selected. – The selected schemes are to be used in the next co-creation activity for defining policy and incentives to facilitate investment in soil health. 	

Table 17: Pre-selection of policy and economic incentives for soil health.

Conducting a SWOT analysis of policy and economic incentives.

Activity title	Conducting a SWOT analysis of policy and economic incentives.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 6.3. Economic and financial innovation schemes in LLs (WP6, leader: CMCC).
Co-organisers	ZABA
Facilitator	LH/LL coordinators.
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To conduct a SWOT analysis of the financial and economic schemes pre-selected for each of the LH/LLs in the activity "Pre-selection of economic and financial incentives for soil health". 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<p>From the pre-selected financial and economic schemes for each LH/LL: participants are expected to select 2 based on their expertise, familiarity in terms of application and sustainability of the schemes (environmental, social and governance considerations). For the selected schemes complete a SWOT analysis by answering the following questions (using sticky notes in a MIRO board):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Strengths: What are the advantages of this scheme? – Weaknesses: On what could this scheme be improved? – Opportunities: What are the good opportunities of the scheme? – Threats: What obstacles do you face with this scheme? 	
When and how?	
Time frame	14 th May 2024.
Format	Online Workshop *For the case of LL1 (Sardinia), a separate workshop was carried out.
Tools	Microsoft Teams & MIRO.
Language	English. Written translations to Spanish provided in the Miro board. For LL1: a separate online workshop in Italian.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
LH/LLs relevant stakeholders. If it is not possible, then LH/LL coordinators can participate instead.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Identify synergies: similarities with other LH/LLs, what are they challenges, and best-practices, strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and strengths. – Learn about the schemes that they did not know before. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The output of this activity is to be used as an input to create a toolbox of incentives schemes (Deliverable D6.3) 	

Table 18: Conducting a SWOT analysis of policy and economic incentives.

Using policy framework analysis to explore a successful implementation of the incentive schemes for ecosystem services delivered by healthy soils across multiple scenarios

Activity title	Using policy framework analysis to explore a successful implementation of the incentive schemes for ecosystem services delivered by healthy soils across multiple scenarios.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 6.3. Economic and financial innovation schemes in LLs (WP6, leader: CMCC).
Co-organisers	ZABA and all LH/LL coordinators.
Facilitator	LH/LL coordinators and collaboration with WP4-5.
What?	
Objective	
– Explore regulatory aspects of economic schemes, experiences of the LH/LL using them and implementation conditions.	
Description of the co-creation activity	
– Organize regular meetings (back and for validation) with LH/LL coordinators to discuss about the implementation of the schemes.	
When and how?	
Time frame	After December 2024.
Format	Meetings.
Tools	Online.
Language	English, local languages.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
All LH/LL coordinators and relevant local stakeholders if needed.	
What is in it for participants?	
– Helping LH/LL coordinators to understand challenges and barriers of applying the economic schemes.	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
– It would feed the Toolbox of incentive schemes (D6.3).	

Table 19: Using policy framework analysis to explore a successful implementation of the incentive schemes for ecosystem services delivered by healthy soils across multiple scenarios.

Sharing of the soil health certification in carbon farming framework with LL&LH stakeholders

Activity title	Sharing of the soil health certification in carbon farming framework with LL&LH stakeholders.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 6.2. Soil health certification approaches (WP6, leader: CMCC).
Co-organisers	ZABA
Facilitator	CMCC
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To evaluate the possibility to complement the carbon farming certification scheme with indicators that ensure the accountability of soil health results beyond carbon, introducing the supplementary indicators provided by WP3. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Each coordinator will select the most important five carbon farming techniques and rank them based on their priority. – Discuss the results of each LH/LL prioritisation. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	June 2024.
Format	Webinar.
Tools	Jamboard (Google online collaboration board).
Language	English.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
LH/LL coordinators.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Learn more about the carbon farming certification framework and increase the relevance of the outcome of soil health certification approaches for their LH/LL. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Soil health certification in carbon farming framework (D6.2). – Analyse the carbon farming certification methodologies in the context of InBestSoil with the possibility of giving feedback to the expert group of European commission working in carbon certification. 	

Table 20: Sharing of the soil health certification in carbon farming framework with LH/LL stakeholders.

Develop policy recommendations based on WP2-WP5 outputs

Activity title	Develop policy recommendations based on WP2-WP5 outputs.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 6.4. Policy recommendations for transformative soil health protection (WP6, leader: CMCC).
Co-organisers	ZABA
Facilitator	CMCC
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To develop policy recommendations based on WP2-WP5 outputs to enhance the role of the EU and national policy frameworks in promoting soil health. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<p>In this co-creation activity CMCC analyse outputs deliver by different WP-s (in two steps):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Set meeting with WP2-WP3-WP4-WP5, if possible, in person. – After a plenary with all WP-s to finalize all the EU and national policy recommendation with all the input. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	(Dec 2026- dec 2027) to be defined more specifically.
Format	Work session (one to one; or plenary: to be confirmed).
Tools	Online (more details to be determined) or maybe in person in a general assembly.
Language	English.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Learn from other WP outputs, make each WP outputs stronger, more impactful. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Policy recommendations for promoting soil health in the EU context. – Scientific paper. 	

Table 21: Develop policy recommendations based on WP2-WP5 outputs.

Communication, dissemination, and exploitation

Communication and dissemination activities play a key role in raising awareness on soil health and in communicating project progress and results. Exploitation activities facilitate maximizing project's results and impacts ensuring results' legacy beyond the project. InBestSoil acknowledges that communication and dissemination activities should always be collaboratively developed, but in this case, an additional effort to include higher participation and co-creation approaches has been made.

For the communication and dissemination aspects of the project two co-creation activities have been defined (Figure 7). Firstly, collaborative communication messages will be developed based on a selection of topics, themes, and channels to ensure that a diversity of target groups are reached out (table 22). Secondly the input from researchers and local partners will be sought to identify a relevant communication topic to follow up on during the project lifetime (table 23).

Figure 8: Diagram representing the co-creation activities in WP7, inputs (in brown) and outputs (in green).

Collaborative messages co-creation for communication & dissemination

Activity title	Collaborative messages co-creation for communication & dissemination.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 7.1. InBestSoil communication strategy and WP7 & Task 7.2. Dissemination strategy (WP7, leader: JUNE).
Co-organisers	LGI
Facilitator	JUNE
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The goal of the workshop, which targets consortium partners, is to discuss and brainstorm potential communication topics to be shared by the consortium partners with the general public through communication via the project's official channels (website, social media) as well as specialized media. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – An invitation for the workshop participation is sent to all LH/LL coordinators and consortium partners. – Participation in a workshop answering different questions, such as "If you were to write an article (press/ blog type) what would you write it about?" that would help to identify important messages to communicate. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	4 th of April 2024.
Format	An online workshop.
Tools	Miro, Microsoft Teams.
Language	English.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
All LH/LL coordinators and WP partners.	
What is in it for participants?	
Consortium partners' opinion and expertise would be considered for the communication plan of the project and strategy update.	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
Gather all the valuable information, messages and knowledge that could be shared in InBestSoil for WP7 – Communication & Dissemination.	

Table 22: Collaborative messages co-creation for communication & dissemination.

Co-identify a topic suitable for the media and public

Activity title	Co-identify a topic suitable for the media and public.
Activity coordinators	
GA Task Leader	Task 7.1. InBestSoil communication strategy (Wp7, leader: JUNE).
Co-organisers	LGI and ZABA.
Facilitator	JUNE
What?	
Objective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To create a survey that would identify a topic suitable for the media and public, analysing insights and knowledge that the communication and dissemination team can track at least 2 times throughout the project. 	
Description of the co-creation activity	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboratively define a survey to identify a topic suitable for media and general public, as well as valuable dissemination results for future events, workshops, etc. - Fill the survey questionnaire by local stakeholders. 	
When and how?	
Time frame	July – October 2024.
Format	Excel document that would be translated into a survey.
Tools	Excel and survey monkey.
Language	English.
For Whom is this activity? and why?	
Target group	
All LH/LL coordinators.	
What is in it for participants?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Help participants to connect with other stakeholders. - Make sure that the communication is more contextualized. - Consider the opinion of all LH/LL for the topic analysis that would be tracked for communication purposes. 	
Expected outcomes for the WP/ Project	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creating a survey that would be used for the selection of a relevant topic for the public. - Survey filled out by local stakeholders providing insights for communication purposes. 	

Table 23: Co-identify a topic suitable for the media and public.

5.Limitations and recommendations

Chapter 5 presents the identified potential limitations to successfully implement the InBestSoil co-creation activities and the recommended strategies to overcome them. In addition, recommendations for the successful implementation of the current plan and its potential replicability in other Mission Soil projects are presented.

Limitations & recommended strategies

Specific challenges might be encountered when implementing a co-creation activity. However, identifying strategies to reduce the limitations can help implementing a co-creation activity successfully. Based on the co-design and co-creation plan validation exercise, the lessons learned from the conducted activities, and the discussions with project partners, a list of general limitations and strategies have been developed (table 24). These are considered preliminary findings as the co-creation activities are an on-going process lasting the project lifetime. Still, identifying limitations and strategies to overcome these at this early stage allows for an iterative process that incorporates learnings into the co-creation plan and future recommendations. This chapter will be updated by the end of the project and included in the final deliverable *D2.4 Co-design and co-creation plan updated*.

Limitations	Recommended strategies
Co-creation activities imply the need for mutual understanding between researchers, practitioners, and local stakeholders. The use of scientific jargon and different communicating forms can create challenges.	Avoid the use of scientific jargon when communicating with stakeholders. A suggestion is to create different materials adapted to the target audience, e.g., create two protocols for sustainable business models development, one using scientific terminology and another one including easier language.
A project consortium is usually constituted by partners from different countries, entities, and expertise. The lack of planning and lack of general overview might reduce the efficiency of the co-creation plan.	For the coordination of all the activities (including planning and implementation), to schedule recurrent (i.e., bimonthly) meetings with project partners is recommended. The purpose of these meetings is to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – facilitate the coordination of agendas. For example, the meeting can be used to discuss the planning and agree on best timing for implementing a co-creation activity in which participation of LH and LL coordinators or local stakeholders is expected. – facilitate the implementation of co-creation activities. For example, the meeting can also be used to conduct a co-creation activity in the form of an online workshop. – reduce the communication by email and increase the oral communications, having room for questions and clarifications. – have a better time management, and thus, reduce the burden on project partners and stakeholders.

	<p>For written communication, it is recommended to develop user-friendly materials. The use of the InBestSoil co-creation activity template (table 1) allows standardising the information and improving the understanding of the co-creation activities in advance (objective, activity format, timing, target participation, expected outcomes).</p>
<p>Low participation, success rate and limited engagement from participants can hamper achieving the expected outcomes.</p>	<p>Create a win-win strategies: co-creation activity goals should be aligned with the needs of participants.</p> <p>Define the benefits of participating for stakeholders. Each stakeholder might benefit in a different form or might be attracted to participate by different reasons. For example, input for policies (governments), expertise (municipalities), or ideas to grow the business (farmers).</p> <p>Define the profile of stakeholders and the minimum and maximum number needed for each activity. Specify the information to be requested from and/or given to stakeholders.</p> <p>To increase the engagement during the activity: share in advance a clear agenda including the benefits of participating, facilitate a dynamic workshop, and make use of user-friendly tools.</p>
<p>The use of non-local language and/or the use of technology (e.g., online activity) can create barriers for participation.</p>	<p>To organise co-creation activities targeting local stakeholders, in person workshops using local language are preferred. In addition, cultural aspects should be considered in the communication.</p> <p>When in person activities are not possible, it is recommended to be consistent and preferably use the same online platform for all activities. It is recommended to start the activity with an icebreaker exercise for getting participants familiarized with the online tool. Assist those participants that cannot use the online platform.</p> <p>When the local language is not known by the organiser, it is recommended to ask other project partners for translation support. For online activities, written translations can be provided even when the local language is not used for facilitating the activity.</p>

Table 24: Limitations and recommended strategies for implementing co-creation activities.

Recommendations and way forward

Soil health projects require multidisciplinary expertise through collaboration, knowledge sharing and co-creation. While each project partner contributes with invaluable knowledge and expertise, expanding beyond individual knowledge by bridging the gap between scientists, practitioners and local stakeholders is key to solve complex problems. Facilitating these interactions and identifying synergies between co-creation activities is an added value of a co-creation plan.

Observations from the InBestSoil project show case that WP and task leaders, as well as LH and LL coordinators find the co-creation plan a useful tool that compiles all the project co-creation activities in a user-friendly document. At early stages of the project, when the co-creation plan was in process, LH and LL coordinators shown concerns about the strategies to interact with stakeholders and the limited information available on the tasks expected from their side. The co-creation plan has facilitated coordinating activities from different WPs that require participation from the same target group in the same time frame.

Based on the preliminary learnings from the InBestSoil project, this section presents general recommendations for developing a co-creation plan. These recommendations can be of added value for other Mission Soil projects, as collaboration and knowledge sharing between researchers, practitioners, and local stakeholders are key for achieving Mission Soil goals. Recommended steps to develop a co-creation plan:

- To build an effective co-creation plan, the definition of the co-creation activities by WP and task leaders is crucial. Thus, giving time at the beginning of the project to WP and task leaders for structuring their activities will facilitate a more effective communication.
- Likewise, it is important to share and validate the co-creation activities proposed with project partners. Although the co-creation activities might happen later in the project, to initiate conversations on the co-creation activities early in the project lifetime is recommended. Otherwise, the time and input needed for the activity design might not be well allocated. Therefore, as soon as the WP and task leaders have drafted their activities, it is interesting that project partners brainstorm along with them. In addition, the perspective of LH and LL coordinators or project case studies should be included at an early stage in the brainstorm process. This allows including valuable information in the activities' definition which will result in more effective activities that meet the objectives.
- Finally, aligning the co-creation activities to be conducted as part of each WP with other project activities is highly recommended. Different co-creation activities might require input from LH and LL coordinators or from the same group of stakeholders. To make the most out of local stakeholders' time and LH and LL efforts, and avoid overlapping and stakeholders burn out, finding ways to combine different activities with similar goals or expectations, might result in more effective and impactful activities.
- The time required for these co-creation sessions is usually underestimated, and projects might have not allocated enough time. In fact, allocating specific financial resources, as well as human resources such as a team specialized on stakeholder coordination is of high added value to facilitate and systematically monitor the interactions and brainstorming sessions. Many projects in one way or another

include collaborative activities but are not always properly registered or documented, hindering activities' replicability and further learnings implementation. When systematically monitored, the outputs can be validated and be considered reliable to contribute to science, policy recommendations and on the ground developments.

Way forward:

This deliverable D2.3 "*Co-design and co-creation plan for stakeholders*" presents the details of the co-creation activities to be conducted throughout the InBestSoil project lifespan. A description of the activities' implementation and any updates to the plan will be included in the deliverable D2.4 "*Co-design and co-creation plan updated*".

Both deliverables are expected to be of use for InBestSoil partners but also for other Mission Soil projects.

Meanwhile, to ensure that all co-creation activities in InBestSoil reach the proposed goals and have a positive impact on soil health and stakeholders' communities, the following actions will be taken:

- Schedule and coordinate bimonthly meetings during the project lifetime: time will be allocated for those co-creation activities that require input in the coming months.
- Facilitate meetings between task leaders and LH and LL coordinators to discuss each co-creation activity to be implemented.
- Conduct coordination meetings between WP2 leaders (ZABA) and other WP and task leaders, as well as with LH and LL coordinators, to facilitate the activities implementation.
- Systematically monitor all the co-creation activities implemented, track the process followed, and record the results.
- Compile the results from all co-creation activities and develop recommendations.

6. References

ⁱ *EU missions, Concrete solutions for our greatest challenges. European Commission. Available at: [EU missions - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#)*

ⁱⁱ *Mission Soil Implementation Plan. 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030. A Soil Deal for Europe. European Commission. Available at: [EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe \(europa.eu\)](#)*

ⁱⁱⁱ *Mission Soil Living Labs and Lighthouses. Mission Soil platform. European Commission. Available at: [Living labs of Mission Soil | Mission Soil Platform \(europa.eu\)](#)*

